

1

2

3

5

6

7

8

9

10

x1

11

x9

12

x4

13

x5

14

15

To prevent the magnets from falling out, use a small amount of blu-tac to cover the holes or gaps the magnets are inserted into. Ensure all magnets in the surface are orientated with the same direction of magnetism.

Please see the notes document for more information about appropriate magnet size and number of magnets.

16

To prevent the magnets from falling out, use a small amount of blu-tac to cover the holes or gaps the magnets are inserted into. Ensure all magnets in the surface are orientated with the same direction of magnetism.

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Either add each block to the base individually, or you can mount them all upside-down.

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19

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21

x3

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23

24

25

x2

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27

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x3

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30

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32

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x2

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At this point, you may wish to tie a string and include the larger fridge-type magnet. Please see the notes document for details.

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You can either slot the potential energy landscape in upright or angle the hinges to install it at an angle and then adjust.

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Rotate the rear pins to prevent the potential energy landscape from falling.

